

New species of Erebidae (Lepidoptera) in the fauna of Tajikistan

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Abstract: *Amata (Syntomis) caspia* Staudinger, 1877 is reported for the first time from Tajikistan. Additional information on the distribution of other species in Tajikistan is also provided.

Keywords: *Amata caspia*, Erebidae, first record, range extension, South Tajikistan

Introduction

Syntomini are a difficult to identify group of moths, as they have strong individual and geographical variability, along with a pronounced sexual dimorphism in wing markings (Ignatyev & Zolotuhin, 2005). They are medium-sized moths with brightly and variegated colored wings. The 1st and 5th segments of the abdomen are ringed in yellow, but of the ring on the 1st segment is less conspicuous and incomplete. Externally, they are similar with day flying Zygaenidae, but differ in the filamentous shape of the antennae, as well as the shape of the wings.

There is almost no information available about the fauna of the Syntomini of Tajikistan, and for years no-one has been studying them. According to Ignatiev & Zolotukhin (2005), there are currently three species and one subspecies of the genus of *Amata* in Tajikistan: *Amata bactriana* Erschoff, 1874, *Amata sovinskiji* (Obraztsov, 1966), *Amata hissarica* (Stshetkin, 1979), *Amata (Syntomis) maracandina pamira* Obraztsov, 1966. The finding of new taxa of Lepidoptera for the fauna of Tajikistan is predictable, since its fauna has not been studied sufficiently. Every year we find new species of butterflies for our fauna (Davlatov, 2022, 2024), but the findings of new Syntomini taxa for Tajikistan was accidental, since our research is focused on collecting Papilionoidea.

During expeditions to South Tajikistan in May collecting was carried out in the Tigrovaya Balka

Nature Reserve, Dusti District. Along with butterflies several specimens of the *Amata* genus were collected, and after studying the material it turned out that they belonged to *Amata caspia* Staudinger, 1877, a species that was not previously known from the territory of Tajikistan.

Results

Amata caspia Staudinger, 1877

Morphology: *Amata caspia* has a green or blue-black body and wings. The antennae are black. The length of the front wing is 17–18 mm. The fore wings have six white spots, and the hind wings only a single white spot. There is a ring on the 1st segment of abdomen is triangular from above, and the 5th is fully ringed yellow. It should be noted that our collected specimens morphologically fully correspond to the nominotypical subspecies and there is no need to for description of a separate subspecies (Fig. 1).

Material: 12 ♂♂ – 10.05.2024, South Tajikistan, Dusti District, Tigrovaya Balka Nature Reserve, 21-block, Korolevskiy Area, 340 m a.s.l., 37°15'20.14"N 068°25'11.75"E (A.M. Davlatov).

The material was collected from a semi-desert landscape with sparse xerophytic vegetation (Fig. 2). *A. caspia* were found in large numbers on the shrubs of the *Zygophyllum gontscharovii* Boriss, but it was

Fig. 1. The Syntomini moths present in Tajikistan: (A) *Amata caspia* Staudinger, 1877, (B) *Amata bactriana* Erschoff, 1874, (C) *Amata hissarica* (Stschetkin, 1979). (Photos by A.M. Davlatov).

Fig 2. Habitats of *Amata caspia* in the Tigrovaya Balka Nature Reserve (Photo by A.M. Davlatov).

not found in the Tugai forest. The caterpillars of this species probably feed on the leaves of *Z. gontscharovii*. According to Tatar et al. (2022), the general habitat of *A. caspia* in Turkey is represented by flowering weeds, elm (*Ulmus minor*) and rocky areas. Like the Zygaenidae, representatives of the Syntomini fly slowly and over a short distance. In most cases, they were observed sitting on plants and in cloudy weather they do not fly at all. We have observed the same behaviour in other species of this group such as *A. bactriana* and *A. hissarica* (Fig. 1, B–C). At the collection places *A. caspia* was common, the other two species *A. hissarica* and *A. bactriana* that were collected last year, were less

abundant occurring singularly. The two additional species were found in the following localities: Material: *A. hissarica* – 1 ♂, 1.07.2023, Tajikistan, Hissar Ridge, Karatag Gorge, 1440 m a.s.l., 38°44'31.37"N 68°21'56.89"E, 1 ♂, 12.06.2023, Tajikistan, Hissar Ridge, Romit Gorge, 1610 m a.s.l., 38°43'30.54"N 69°18'06.31"E (A.M. Davlatov); *A. bactriana* – 2 ♂♂, 8.07.2023, Tajikistan, the Fann Mountains, Hissar Ridge, the neighbourhood of Iskandarkul Lake, 2590 m a.s.l., 39°05'03.11"N 68°24'37.32"E (A.M. Davlatov). Both species (*A. hissarica*, *A. bactriana*) were collected on rocky slopes with woody-shrubby vegetation.

Distribution of *Amata caspia*: Southern European Russia, South Urals, southern West Siberia, the Caucasus, Transcaspiian Region, Mongolia, Western China, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan and Afghanistan. Our finding fills a distribution gap *A. caspia* in Central Asia.

Notes: For the Vakhsh Valley of Tajikistan, Stschetkin (1960) provides the *A. minuta* A. Bang-Haas, 1910, but at the same time notes that it probably can be a form of *A. caspia*, which can be solved only by accumulating significant material. Ignatev & Zolotukhin (2005) do not indicate the distribution of *A. caspia* for Tajikistan. Unfortunately, the fate of Stschetkin's collection is unknown, so no one can reliably confirm the species identity of the Syntomids specimen he collected in 1960. Given the uncertainty in Stschetkin's work (1960), as well as the lack of indication of the distribution of *A. caspia* for Tajikistan in Ignatev & Zolotukhin's work (2005), we can say with confidence that the *A. caspia* collected by us is undoubtedly the first find of this taxon in Tajikistan.

Conclusion

The study of the Syntomini of Tajikistan is compatible with butterfly surveys and will continue in the future. It is possible that further research will lead to the discovery of additional species in Tajikistan.

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